

The Transition from Informal to Formal Understanding: Connecting the Concept of Ordering to Order Relation

İnformal Bilgiden Formal Bilgiye Geçiş: Sıralama Kavramını Sıralama Bağıntısı ile İlişkilendirme

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ÖZET

Sıralama bağıntısı soyut matematiğin önemli kavramlarından biri olup, sıralama bağıntıları sayesinde bir kümenin elemanları sıralanabilir ve bu kümenin maksimum, minimum, supremum, infimum maksimal ve minimal elemanları belirlenebilir. Dolayısıyla matematikte veya günlük hayatta herhangi bir sıralamadan söz edildiğinde farkında olmasak da dip metinde bir sıralama bağıntısı kullanılır. Oysa öğrenciler genelde sıralama kavramı ile sıralama bağıntısının bu ilişkisinin farkında olmayıp, sıralama bağıntısının sadece belli özellikleri sağlayan bir bağıntı olduğunu düşünmektedirler. Bu bağlamda informal olarak günlük hayatta kullanılan sıralama kavramının, akademik yaşantıda sıralama bağıntıları ile ilişkilendirilmesi gerektiği söylenebilir. Bu makalede İlköğretim Matematik Öğretmenliği 1. sınıflarda öğrenim gören öğretmen adaylarının sıralama kavramını sıralama bağıntısıyla ilişkilendirme düzeyleri Tall ve Vinner (1981)'in kavram imgesi ve kavram tanımı teorik perspektifi göz önüne alınarak yorumsal ve açıklayıcı tarzda sunulmaya çalışılmıştır. Bu çalışma, soyut matematik dersinde sıralama bağıntıları konusu işlendikten sonra öğretmen adaylarının sıralama kavramı hakkındaki informal bilgilerinin, nasıl ve ne derece formal bilgiye çevrildiğinin ayrıntılı bir raporudur. Öğretmen adaylarının sıralama kavramı ile ilgili hem informal hem de formal düzeyde çeşitli kavram imgelerine sahip oldukları tespit edilmiş, sıralama kavramına ilişkin düşüncelerinde, reel sayılardaki adi sıralamanın ($1 < 3$, $3 < 5$ vb.) hâkim olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Buna paralel olarak öğretmen adaylarının sıralama kavramını, sıralama bağıntısı ile ilişkilendirmede yani kavramı formal olarak anlamada çeşitli güçlükler yaşadıkları tespit edilmiş, bu güçlüklerle ilişkin öneriler sunulmuştur. Katılımcılardan toplanan nitel veriler, öğretmen adaylarının sıralama kavramına matematiksel açıdan sağlam ve çok yönlü bir perspektif ile bakabilmeleri için dikkat edilmesi gereken hususları ortaya çıkarmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sıralama Kavramı, Sıralama Bağıntısı, Kavram İmgesi, Kavram Tanımı.

ABSTRACT

Order relation is one of the fundamental concepts in abstract mathematics. By using order relations, the elements of a set can be ordered and the maximum, minimum, supreme, infimum, maximal and minimal elements of the set can be determined. Therefore, whenever any ordering is mentioned in mathematics or daily life, we can argue that order relation is an intrinsic part of this comparison, even if we are not explicitly aware of it. However, it is often assumed that students may not recognize the connections between the everyday use of ordering and the formal concept of order relation introduced at the university level. In this context, the concept of order, as used informally in daily life, should be associated with the concept of order relation in an academic setting. This article aims to present the extent to which prospective mathematics teachers associate the concept of order with order relations, interpreted through the theoretical framework of concept image and concept definition as proposed by Tall and Vinner (1981). The study provides a detailed account of how and to what extent the informal knowledge of prospective teachers about the concept of order was transformed into formal understanding after the topic of order relations was covered in the abstract mathematics course. The findings indicate that prospective teachers possess various concept images regarding the notion of order, both at informal and formal levels, and that the familiar usage of order (e.g., $1 < 3$, $3 < 5$) dominates their understanding. In parallel with this, it was revealed that prospective teachers have several difficulties in grasping the notion of order formally, and several suggestions are provided to address these challenges.

Keywords: Concept of Ordering, Order Relation, Concept Image, Concept Definition.

INTRODUCTION

Concepts and notations in abstract mathematics form the foundation of mathematics and enable the effective use of mathematical language, foster an understanding of the origins of concepts, and support the development of solid mathematical understanding. From this perspective, the importance of abstract mathematics should not be disregarded alongside concrete mathematics, which is practical and generally perceived as more useful by individuals. Another important focus in mathematics education is research

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conducted at the university level. The term "university level" refers to courses taught in primary and secondary mathematics teacher training programs in our country. The mathematics courses taught in these programs, which aim to train teachers in the best possible way, are important for prospective teachers, i.e., future teachers. One of the courses that will best equip prospective teachers with the fundamental language of mathematics is undoubtedly abstract mathematics.

The concepts of ordering and order relations are also important concepts in abstract mathematics. However, they can be difficult for students to grasp and are prone to misconceptions and learning difficulties. Because prospective primary and secondary mathematics teachers, especially at the university level, fail to connect the concept of ordering with ordering relations, the concept of ordering is limited to the ordinary ordering we know ($1 < 3$, $3 < 5$, $1 < 5$) for most students. The fact that there can be other forms of ordering and that symbols such as \square , $\#$, \blacktriangle , \circ can be compared or that 3 can be greater than 4 when related to the concept of order relations are mathematical concepts that are not easily formed in students' minds. Furthermore, considering the abstract nature of mathematics and the epistemological obstacles inherent in the concept, it is natural that even university students may experience difficulties with the aforementioned types of ordering.

In relation to the concept of ordering, it may be necessary to first discuss order theory. Order theory is a branch of mathematics that studies the priority order of ordered pairs through binary relations. It examines situations such as "this is smaller than that" or "this comes before that." Order theory can be defined as a branch of mathematics that uses binary relations to investigate our intuitive beliefs about ordering. At this point, order theory can provide a formal framework for defining the concept of ordering in terms of statements such as "this is smaller than that" or "this comes before that" (Vishwanath, 2011). Order theory gains meaning when considering the ordering relations. If a relation \leq defined on a non-empty set A satisfies the properties of reflexivity, anti-symmetry, and transitivity, then the relation \leq is called a partial order relation or simply an order relation on the set A . The structure denoted by (A, \leq) is called a partially ordered set or poset. In a poset (A, \leq) , if $(a, b) \in \leq$, then the elements a and b are called comparable elements of the poset; otherwise, the elements of a pair not belonging to the relation are called "incomparable." If $(a, b) \in \leq$, then the element a in the first component comes before or is less than the element b in the second component, or the element b comes after or is greater than the element a (Güney & Özkoç, 2015).

Once an order relation has been defined, examining the concept of ordering in relation to it will give meaning to the concept itself. In fact, with the three properties mentioned above, order relations form the basis and mathematical logic of the concept of ordering. The act of comparison inherent in the concept of ordering actually requires the use of order relations without us being aware of it. The comparability and incomparability situations within the topic of order relations, the ability to order objects and elements that appear to be unrelated, whether a set is bounded or not, its lower and upper bounds, finiteness-infiniteness, and other concepts will form the basis for prospective teachers to transition from informal to formal knowledge about the concept of ordering and to develop a full conceptual understanding of the nature of the field. Indeed, considering that the topic of relations plays an important role in the formation of other topics in mathematics (e.g., functions), the necessity of learning the concepts of ordering and order relations within the topic of relations in a comprehensive manner is once again highlighted.

It can be argued that mathematical connections play a critical role in learning and understanding mathematical concepts. Mathematical connections can also be defined as the thoughts and processes used to establish links among different topics in mathematics (Heibert & Carpenter, 1992). Eli, Mohr-Schroeder, and Lee (2013) view mathematical connections as the components of a schema within a mental network. Making connections can be categorized into four subcomponents: connections between mathematical concepts, connections between different representations of mathematical concepts, connections with real-world applications of mathematics, and connections between mathematics and other fields (Bingölbali & Çoşkun, 2016). In this context, understanding the concept of ordering by making a connection with the order relation corresponds to establishing connections between mathematical concepts, which constitutes one of the fundamental components of mathematical connections and plays a critical role in the formal learning of the concept of ordering.

A review of the literature reveals that there are very few studies on the concept of ordering and the order relation at the university level in the field of mathematics education. In this respect, this study plays an important role in filling this gap in the field. A review of the literature reveals that there are only studies on the concept of ordering at the primary education level and on some concepts in algebra at the university level. Thomaidis and Tzanakis (2007) investigated the historical development of the order relation on the number line and the ways in which students cope with the ordering relation on the number line. However, this study focuses on ordinary ordering in the conventional sense. Kar, Çiltaş, and Işık (2011) examined learning disabilities related to certain concepts in algebra among prospective elementary mathematics teachers. In their study, they determined that students had difficulties in defining basic concepts, distinguishing the differences between concepts, and expressing concepts using mathematical language. Polat and Şahiner (2007) identified and classified common mistakes made by prospective primary teachers regarding relations and functions and sought to answer whether these mistakes could be eliminated. They demonstrated that these mistakes could be largely corrected through the lesson plan and methods used. Schindler and Hußmann (2013) investigated individuals' ideas about ordering relationships in integers to examine students' views on negative integers before introducing the concept of negative integers. This study can be considered in terms of ordinary ordering.

Theoretical Framework

In order to identify misconceptions in students' understanding of mathematical concepts and the difficulties they encounter, analyzing the collected data within a theoretical framework allows for more robust interpretation. One of the theories that examines concept formation and serves as the theoretical framework for this study is the concept image and concept definition theoretical framework proposed by Tall and Vinner (1981).

A crucial point in learning concepts correctly is whether the image formed in students' minds is consistent with the definition given by the instructor. This can be explained through the concept image and concept definition. According to Tall and Vinner (1981), concept definition and concept image are distinct concepts. Concept definition is the form of expression used to explain a concept in detail. The term concept image is used to describe the entire cognitive structure related to a concept. These include mental images, related characteristics, and processes. Concept images are formed over the years through an individual's experiences and may change as the individual encounters new stimuli. Concept images may differ significantly from formal concept definitions and may often be inconsistent with the formal definition. Furthermore, considering that concept images represent the relationship between the individual and the concept, it can be said that they may vary from individual to individual (Bingölbali, 2016). When we briefly refer to concept definition, formal rules and definitions in textbooks come to mind. However, concept images are the images formed in individuals' minds in relation to these formal definitions (Tall & Vinner, 1981). According to Vinner (1983), the examples students encounter during the teaching process may cause them to have inaccurate concept images. Although the relationship between image and misconception is not generally discussed within the theoretical framework of concept definition and concept image, incorrect images can also lead to misconceptions due to overgeneralization (Bingölbali, 2016). On the other hand, even if we do not have concept definitions for some concepts, we may still have concept images about them. However, for some concepts, concept definitions are necessary in order to have concept images. In other words, in addition to the formal concept images, the informal concept images may also exist (Vinner, 1983). In this context, it can be assumed that informal knowledge about the concept of ordering exists. This is because the concept of ordering is used by everyone in some way in daily life. When the formal definition of the order relation is given, students can reconstruct their images of the ordering concept by relating them to the order relation.

Research Problem and Research Questions

This study is part of a more comprehensive thesis. The aim of this study is to reveal how and to what extent the informal knowledge of prospective teachers about the concept of ordering-before the topic of order relations is introduced-is transformed into formal knowledge after it is addressed in an abstract mathematics course. In addition, the study seeks to identify how issues such as comparability and incomparability emerge in the context of order relations, what difficulties arise during this process, and

the possible reasons for these difficulties. Accordingly, the main research problem and research questions are formulated as follows.

Research Problem

"What concept images do prospective mathematics teachers hold regarding the concept of ordering when examined in connection with the order relation?"

Research Questions

1. What informal knowledge do prospective teachers hold about the concept of ordering before encountering the topic of order relations?
2. What formal knowledge do prospective teachers hold about the concept of ordering after encountering the topic of order relations?
3. What difficulties do prospective teachers face in transitioning from an informal to a formal understanding of the concept of ordering?

METHOD

This research used a qualitative, in-depth exploratory case study approach to investigate prospective mathematics teachers' awareness of the ordering concept. Qualitative research can be defined as "research that uses qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interviews, and document analysis, and follows a qualitative process aimed at presenting perceptions and events in a realistic and comprehensive manner in their natural environment" (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008, p.39). In this study, content analysis, one of the types of qualitative data analysis, was used. Content analysis is defined as a systematic, repeatable technique in which certain words in a text are summarized into smaller content categories based on specific rules (Büyüköztürk, Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, & Demirel, 2013). This research was designed as a case study, which is one of the qualitative research methods. Mcmillan (2000) defines a case study as a method that involves the in-depth examination of one or more events, environments, programs, social groups, or other interconnected systems. Case studies are commonly used to (Gall, Borg & Gall, 1996):

- ✓ explain and observe the details that constitute a case,
- ✓ present possible explanations related to a case,
- ✓ evaluate a case.

Study Group

The study group was determined using a multi-stage sampling technique implemented in two phases. In the first phase, 100 first-year students in the Department of Elementary Mathematics Teaching at a state university in Turkey were selected using convenience sampling, which is a type of purposive sampling. The Ordering Concept Knowledge Test (OCKT), consisting of five open-ended questions, was applied to these prospective teachers. Convenience sampling allows the researcher to select situations that are relatively easy to access, thereby contributing to the feasibility of the research (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). In the second phase, the students to be included in the semi-structured interviews were selected using maximum variation sampling, another purposive sampling method. The aim of maximum variation sampling is to form a relatively small sample that maximizes the diversity of individuals involved in the study (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). In this context, five prospective teachers were selected for semi-structured interviews based on their OCKT results. Specifically, in addition to students who provided average responses, those who provided the most accurate answers to the open-ended questions in the OCKT were also included in the semi-structured interviews.

Data Collection Instruments

The data collection instrument used in the research was the Ordering Concept Knowledge Test (OCKT), consisting of five open-ended questions developed with the support of expert reviewers. The questions aimed to assess:

- ✓ the theoretical significance of the concept of ordering,

- ✓ the ordering of elements and items that appear to be unrelated to each other,
- ✓ the existence of alternative types of ordering beyond the conventional notion of ordinary ordering,
- ✓ how the definition of the order relation is conceptualized by prospective teachers.

The specific questions included in the OCKT were as follows:

Q1. “What comes to mind when you hear the phrase, ‘notion of order’?”

Q2. “Can the symbols $\square, \Delta, \#, *$ be ordered? If yes, show how you would order them.”

Q3. “Is there any ordering where 3 is greater than 4 within the concept of ordering? If yes, write your justification and exemplify it.”

Q4. “Is there any set where any two different elements can’t be compared with each other in terms of greatness-smallness? Write your justification and exemplify it.”

Q5. “What is order relation? Define it.”

In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted with five prospective teachers to further explore the reasoning underlying their written responses to the OCKT. Each interview lasted approximately 10–15 minutes. A separate interview protocol was not developed; instead, the OCKT questions served as the basis for the interviews. During the interviews, the researcher posed follow-up questions derived from the participants’ written responses and their answers provided in real time, in order to gain deeper insights into their understanding.

Data Analysis

Content analysis was applied to the written data obtained from the OCKT. Content analysis involves stages such as coding the data, identifying themes, organizing the data according to codes and themes, and interpreting the findings (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013).

In the analysis of the collected data, the theoretical framework of concept image and concept definition proposed by Tall and Vinner (1981) and frequencies were used to describe the data. The prospective teachers’ responses were compiled and categorized into codes, and each response was assigned to the appropriate code. To ensure the validity and reliability, the coding scheme was independently reviewed by another mathematics educator. The inter-coder reliability was calculated as 76%, which is considered an acceptable level in qualitative research.

According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2013), strategies for enhancing validity and reliability in qualitative research include extending the researcher’s engagement with the context, employing data triangulation, sharing results with participants to obtain feedback, and consulting peers in the same field regarding the accuracy of findings. In this study, the researcher extended engagement with the research context, employed multiple data collection methods, sought expert review throughout the process, and took measures to enhance the credibility, validity, and reliability of the findings.

FINDINGS

This section presents findings related to the OCKT, which was designed to assess prospective teachers’ informal knowledge of the concept of ordering through open-ended questions. For each question, possible concept images were identified, numbered, and summarized in tables.

Since the OCKT was administered twice- prior to and after the introduction of the formal definition of order relations and related concepts-the frequencies of the identified concept images are presented in the tables to reflect these two phases. These phases are denoted as **B.D** (*Before encountering Definition*), referring to prospective teachers who had not yet been introduced to the concept of order relations, and **A.F** (*After encountering Definition*), referring to those who had received instruction on the topic. This design was intended to reveal differences in the transition from informal to formal knowledge.

Concept images are numbered as Ci1, Ci2, Ci3, and so forth. These images are illustrated and explained on a question-by-question basis. In addition, responses not considered as representing a concept image-for example, blank answers or statements such as “cannot be ordered” without further justification-are also included in the tables, though they are not assigned concept image codes.

Findings Regarding Question 1 of the OCKT

The purpose of the first question, "What comes to mind when you hear the phrase, 'notion of order'?", was to elicit prospective teachers' informal knowledge of ordering. Specifically, this question aimed to reveal their concept images of ordering prior to receiving formal instruction on the topic. An overview of the data is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Categories Regarding Question 1 of the OCKT

Question	Concept Image or Category	*B.D (f)	A.D (f)
Q1	Ci1: Feeling the need for a specific criterion or rule	81	66
	Ci2: Recalling the order relation - associating with the formal definition	-	23
	Ci3: The necessity of having common features among the elements to be ordered	8	-
	Ci4: The concept of permutation	5	-
	Ci5: Grouping and classification of elements	-	4
	Ci6: Ordering with or without criteria	3	-
	Other	3	7

*B.D: Before encountering definitions, A.D: After encountering definitions

The categories presented in Table 1 are explained in detail below. Blank responses or answers such as "cannot be ordered" without justification were categorized under **Other**.

Ci1: Feeling the need for a specific criterion or rule

This category refers to preservice teachers who emphasized the necessity of applying a specific rule when ordering items, numbers, or elements. Examples of responses related to this image are provided below, divided into before encountering the definitions (B.D) and after encountering the definitions (A.D). Participants were coded using the initials of their first and last names.

F.C (B.D): *"It can be considered as the ordering of objects, numbers or figures according to rules."*

A.Y (A.D): *"I think of ordering as arranging data within the framework of a specific rule."*

In the B.D phase, 81 prospective teachers emphasized the use of criteria or rules in their responses. Among them, five explicitly described ordering as the "grouping of elements," while two interpreted the ordering process as "only the numerical data can be ordered"

In response to the first question, which investigated how the concept of ordering was understood, the number of prospective teachers whose concept image corresponded to "feeling the need for a specific criterion or rule" decreased from 81 to 66 after they were introduced to the topic of order relations. This decrease can be explained by the emergence of a new category in which 23 prospective teachers associated ordering with the formal definition of an order relation. This suggests that the perceived need for external criteria or rules was partially satisfied by the introduction of the formal concept of order relation.

Ci2: Recalling the order relation - associating with the formal definition

As seen in Table 1, 23% of prospective teachers (23 participants) answered the question "What comes to mind when you hear the phrase, 'notion of order'?" by associating it with order relations.

B.B (A.D): *"When I think of ordering, the order relation comes to mind. The order relation ranks the elements."*

In the B.D phase, no prospective teachers were placed in this category. This indicates that prior to formal instruction, the concept of ordering was not associated with order relations by the participants.

Ci3: The necessity of having common features among the elements to be ordered

This category refers to prospective teachers who interpret the concept of ordering as the arrangement of elements that share a common characteristic. Examples of responses include:

S.A (B.D): *"It is the ordering of elements that share a common feature, arranged according to certain characteristics."*

H.C (B.D): *“Ordering is defined as comparing elements that share common characteristics.”*

However, this concept image was not observed in the responses to the first question after the introduction of formal definitions.

Ci4: The concept of permutation

This category refers to prospective teachers' responses that directly associated the concept of ordering to the concept of permutation. These participants interpreted ordering task as different arrangements of certain elements. As shown in Table 1, five prospective teachers classified under this category. A representative written response is presented below.

K.Ç (B.D): *“combining given elements into pairs, triplets, or quadruplets using permutation rules”*

Ci5: Grouping and classification of elements

At the informal level (B.D), Ci5 did not emerge. Prospective teachers categorized under Ci5 interpreted the concept of ordering as grouping or classifying the given elements. An illustrative response is provided below:

P.Ö (A.D): *“It refers to grouping objects, numbers or concepts according to certain characteristics.”*

However, the act of classification or grouping is not consistent with the nature of ordering. Grouping elements aligns more closely with the nature of equivalence relations, in which equivalence classes correspond to categories of grouped elements.

In contrast, the concept of ordering emphasizes arranging elements in a sequence and comparing them. Therefore, the responses of prospective teachers in this category suggest a misconception, as they confused the notion of ordering with that of classification.

Ci6: Ordering with or without criteria

This category refers to prospective teachers who indicated that ordering elements does not necessarily require a specific criterion. In other words, they considered that elements could be arranged randomly, without adherence to a particular condition.

A.B (B.D): *“It is the arrangement of existing things according to a certain rule and also without any rule.”*

When Ci5 and Ci6 are considered together, the image of *“ordering with or without criteria”* appeared before the introduction of formal definitions but disappeared afterward. Instead, the image of *“grouping and classification of elements”* emerged following instruction on order relations.

To support the written data, semi-structured interviews were conducted with prospective teachers on this question. An excerpt is presented below. RS represents the researcher and PT the prospective teachers (this notation is followed throughout).

RS: *“What do you think about the concept of ordering? What comes to mind when you hear the term 'ordering'?”*

PT1: *“Arranging certain elements, such as the elements of a set, according to specific characteristics, by establishing a rule in advance and then ordering them accordingly.”*

PT2: *“Arranging certain elements or items according to a given characteristic.”*

RS: *“So, when ordering certain elements, do you think a criterion or standard is necessary?”*

PT1: *“Yes, we need to know what criteria to use for ordering them.”*

PT2: *“Yes, I think it's necessary. You can't order things without a specific rule.”*

PT3: *“Yes, a certain rule is necessary. Ordering is not possible without a criterion.”*

RS: *“Should the elements or items to be ordered have something in common? For example, can unrelated elements such as 3, c, Δ , & be ordered?”*

PT1: " I think they can. We can order these elements using an order relation. If they are elements of such a relation, they can be ordered, even if they don't share common features."

PT2: "I think they can be ordered, but a rule for ordering must be provided. Maybe we can first order shapes and symbols among themselves, and then numbers and letters among themselves."

PT3: "I think they should be of the same type, sharing a common feature. Otherwise, unrelated elements cannot be ordered. For example, while we can say a triangle (Δ) has three sides, we cannot say anything about elements such as & and c."

As the interview excerpts indicate, PT1, PT2, and PT3 all emphasized the need for rules and criteria in ordering. PT3 insisted that unrelated elements without common features cannot be ordered, whereas PT1's suggestion—that seemingly unrelated symbols such as 3, c, Δ , and &, could be ordered through order relations—may be considered a noteworthy perspective at the informal level.

As shown in Table 1, even after formal instruction, the extent to which prospective teachers connected the concept of ordering with order relations (23 participants) remained limited, suggesting that this connection was not adequately established.

Findings Regarding Question 2 of the OCKT

The analysis of prospective teachers' responses to the second question of the OCKT — “Can the symbols \square , Δ , #, * be ordered? If yes, show how you would order them.” — revealed the concept image categories summarized in Table 2. The purpose of this question was to investigate the concept images held by prospective teachers regarding the ordering of elements or items that appear unrelated. Explanations of these categories are provided below.

Table 2: Categories Regarding Questions 2 of the OCKT

Question	Concept Image or Category	*B.D (f)	A.D (f)
Q2	Ci7: Determining an arbitrary rule	37	17
	Ci2: Recalling the order relation - associating with the formal definition	-	60
	Ci4: The concept of permutation	19	4
	Ci8: It cannot be ordered because no rule/criteria are given	13	-
	Ci3: The necessity of having common features among the elements to be ordered	15	-
	Ci9: Only the numerical data can be ordered	7	-
	Ci10: The concept of combination	2	-
	Cannot be ordered (no justification)	-	7
	Other	7	12

*B.D: Before encountering definitions, A.D: After encountering definitions

Ci7: Determining an arbitrary rule

In analyzing responses to the second question of the OCKT, 37 prospective teachers were classified under this category. This concept image reflects responses in which the participants ordered the given symbols based on an arbitrary rule or a self-determined criterion. Representative examples are provided below:

A.A (B.D): "We can arrange them in the order in which they appear on the paper, from left to right. \square , Δ , #, *"

U.B (B.D): "They can be ranked by the number of lines in their structures. $\square = \# > \Delta = *$."

As shown in Table 2, the prevalence of this concept image decreased after the introduction of formal definitions, indicating that prospective teachers were less likely to rely on arbitrary rules once they were introduced to order relations.

Ci2: Recalling the order relation - associating with the formal definition

As can be seen in Table 2, 60 prospective teachers responded to Q2 by relating the ordering of symbols to the formal definition. This category did not emerge prior to the introduction of the formal definition. Of these 60 participants, 51 defined and ordered the symbols using an appropriate order relation, while 9 did not define an order relation but stated verbally that the symbols could be ordered through such a relation. Representative excerpts from participants' written responses are provided below.

M.D (A.D): "We can order. If we define an order relation on the set $\{\square, \Delta, \#, *\}, \leq = \{(\square, \square), (\Delta, \Delta), (\#, \#), (*, *), (\square, \Delta), (\Delta, *), (\square, *), (\#, *)\}$, we can write $\square \leq \Delta, \Delta \leq *, \square \leq *$ and $\# \leq *$."

S.A (A.D):

Figure 1: The response given by the student coded as S.A

Ci4: The concept of permutation

This category refers to prospective teachers' responses to Question 2 of the OCKT that invoked the concept of permutation, interpreting ordering as different possible arrangements of the given symbols. As shown in Table 2, 19 prospective teachers were classified under this category in the B.D phase. After they were introduced to the fundamental definitions of order relations, the frequency of this category decreased to 4 in the A.D phase. These four participants stated in their written responses that the arrangements formed by ordering the four symbols would result in $4!$ possible sequences.

A.Y (T.Ö):

Figure 2: The response given by the student coded as A.Y

Ci8: It cannot be ordered because no rule/criteria are given

Before encountering the formal definitions of order relations, prospective teachers in this category indicated that the symbols in Question 2 of the OCKT could not be ordered because no explicit rule was provided. Their responses suggest that a criterion was perceived as indispensable for ordering. In the A.D phase, however, this category did not appear at all. A representative response from this category is provided below:

R.M (B.D): "We cannot order these elements because the basis for ordering has not been specified."

Ci3: The necessity of having common features among the elements to be ordered

Prospective teachers categorized under Ci3 considered that the given symbols could not be ordered because they did not share a common feature. Accordingly, 15 prospective teachers were identified in the B.D phase, whereas this category did not appear at all in the A.D phase. A representative written response is provided below:

H.Ö (B.D): "They cannot be ordered, because they do not share any common features."

Ci9: Only the numerical data can be ordered

This category refers to prospective teachers who stated that only numerical data could be ordered, and that ordering was not possible for symbols that did not carry numerical value. In the B.D phase, 7 prospective teachers were identified in this category.

Ci10: The concept of combination

This category, related to Question 2 of the OCKT, emerged from prospective teachers' responses that associated the given symbols " $\square, \Delta, \#, *$ " with the concept of combination. In this view, ordering was interpreted through the use of combinations. A representative response is provided below:

P.G (B.D): “□, Δ or □, # or □, * or Δ, # or Δ, * or #, * can be ordered as C (4,2) or C (4,3).”

In Question 2, which asked whether the symbols could be ordered, several concept images emerged prior to instruction, including “determining an arbitrary rule,” “it cannot be ordered because no rule/criterion are given,” “the necessity of having common features,” and “only numerical data can be ordered.” After encountering the formal definitions, these categories either disappeared or decreased in frequency. This shift can be explained by the emergence of the concept image “recalling the order relation – associating with the formal definition.”

Nevertheless, even after formal instruction, seven prospective teachers continued to emphasize that ordering these symbols was not possible. This persistence suggests that the idea of ordering non-numerical or seemingly unrelated symbols conflicted with the intuitive conceptions of some prospective teachers.

Findings Regarding Question 3 of the OCKT

An analysis of the prospective teachers’ responses to the third question of the OCKT, "Is there any ordering where 3 is greater than 4 within the concept of ordering? If yes, write your justification and exemplify it" revealed the concept image categories summarized in Table 3. This question was designed to reveal prospective teachers’ concept images of ordering, particularly those that may conflict with their everyday perceptions. Explanations of these categories are provided below.

Table 3: Categories Regarding Questions 3 of the OCKT

Question	Concept Image or Category	*B.D (f)	A.D (f)
Q3	Ci7: Determining an arbitrary rule	32	10
	Ci2: Recalling the order relation - associating with the formal definition	-	73
	Cannot be ordered (Unjustified)	44	4
	Can be ordered (Unjustified)	15	-
	Other	9	13

* B.D: Before encountering definitions, A.D: After encountering definitions

Ci7: Determining an arbitrary rule

This category refers to prospective teachers who demonstrated, by applying their own arbitrary rule, that there could be an ordering in which 3 was greater than 4. As shown in Table 3, 32 prospective teachers were classified in this category during the B.D phase, while in the A.D phase the frequency decreased to 10. Representative responses are provided below:

A.T (B.D): "It is possible, because in a ranking where the duration is taken as the basis, those who finish in a shorter time will be at the top. Thus, those with a duration of 3 will be ahead of those with a duration of 4."

K.L (B.D): "It's possible, in the number 34, 3>4. 3 is in the tens digits and 4 in the units digit. Here, the value of 3 is greater than 4."

For this question, which asked whether an ordering could exist in which 3 is greater than 4, the frequency of the concept image “determining an arbitrary rule” decreased from 32 to 10. This dramatic decrease indicates a shift toward Ci2, as more prospective teachers began associating ordering with the formal definition of order relations.

Ci2: Recalling the order relation - associating with the formal definition

There were 73 prospective teachers in the A.D phase for Question 3 of the OCKT. Of these, 59 defined an appropriate mathematical ordering relation to demonstrate that an ordering in which 3 is greater than 4 is possible. Fourteen participants, however, only stated verbally that such an ordering could be possible through order relations, without providing a formal definition. Before encountering the fundamental concepts of order relations (B.D), this concept image did not emerge.

These findings suggest that prospective teachers’ informal, everyday-life conceptions of ordering were limited to ordinary orderings involving real numbers. A representative written response is provided below for illustrative purposes.

P.G (A.D):

Figure 3: The response given by the student coded as P.G

“Cannot be ordered (Unjustified)”

As seen in Table 3, prospective teachers in this category stated that an ordering in which 3 is greater than 4 could not exist, yet they offered no clear justification for this claim.

“Can be ordered (Unjustified)”

As seen in Table 3, prospective teachers in this category stated that an ordering in which 3 is greater than 4 was possible, but they did not provide any explicit justification to support their response.

Findings Regarding Question 4 of the OCKT

When the written responses to the fourth question of the OCKT— “*Is there any set where any two different elements cannot be compared with each other in terms of greatness or smallness? Write your justification and exemplify it.*”—were analyzed, the concept image categories shown in Table 4 were identified. This question aimed to reveal prospective teachers’ views on whether all elements in a set can always be ordered based on order relations.

Table 4: Categories Regarding Questions 4 of the OCKT

Question	Concept Image or Category	*B.D (f)	A.D (f)
Q4	Ci2: Recalling the order relation - associating with the formal definition	-	79
	Ci3: The necessity of having common features among the elements to be ordered	51	6
	Ci9: Only the numerical data can be ordered	27	5
	Elements are always comparable (Unjustified)	10	3
	Other	12	7

* B.D: Before encountering definitions, A.D: After encountering definitions

As shown in Table 4, after instruction on order relations in abstract mathematics, the majority of prospective teachers developed the concept image Ci2 (*recalling the order relation – associating with the formal definition*). Notably, this image did not emerge at all in the B.D phase. However, some prospective teachers continued to exhibit images labeled Ci3 and Ci9, indicating that they remained influenced by informal, everyday-life intuitions.

In addition, several responses were categorized under “*elements are always comparable (Unjustified)*.” These prospective teachers claimed that the elements of a set can always be compared but did not provide justification for this claim. A representative response is provided below:

K.D (A.D): ““*It is possible. For example, in the set $A = \{a, b, c, 1, 2, 3, \square, \blacktriangle\}$, the elements 1,2 and 3 can be compared, but the elements a, b, c, \square and \blacktriangle , which lack numerical value, cannot be compared with each other.*”

This suggests that prospective teachers who believed that non-numerical elements could not be compared experienced difficulties in recognizing that such elements can still be ordered through an appropriate order relation.

To complement the written responses, excerpts from interviews with prospective teachers are presented below:

RS: “*Can there be elements in a set that cannot be ordered or compared with one another?*” *What are your thoughts on this?*

PT3: “*Yes, I think there may be incomparable elements. If two elements in a set are unrelated and have nothing in common, such as 1 and a, they cannot be compared.*”

PT5: “*I think every element can be ordered within a rule. But if we consider elements like a, b, and c, these three letters do not carry numerical values, so they cannot be ordered*”

PT2: “For example, let's consider the elements Δ and 4. I think these elements cannot be compared. Because they are very different elements.”

RS: “However, in your previous answers, you said that elements such as ‘3, c, Δ , &’ could be compared and ordered if a rule is given. Isn't there a contradiction?”

PT2: “Yes, there is a contradiction at this point. But ultimately, I think these elements can be compared in some way. I think every element can be compared if a rule is established.”

Findings Regarding Question 5 of the OCKT

Order relations can be formally defined as follows: If a relation β on a non-empty set satisfies reflexivity, anti-symmetry, and transitivity, then β is called an order relation (Güney & Özkoç, 2015).

From this perspective, when the responses to the fifth question of the OCKT— “What is an order relation? Define it.”—were analyzed, it was found that 8 prospective teachers were able to provide a formal definition in the B.D phase, whereas 92 were unable to do so.

Table 5: Categories Regarding Questions 5 of the OCKT

Question	Concept Image or Category	*B.D (f)	A.D (f)
Q5	Those who provided the formal definition	8	84
	Those unable to provide a formal definition	92	16

* B.D: Before encountering definitions, A.D: After encountering definitions

In the A.D phase, 84 participants were able to provide a formal definition of order relations, while 16 were unable to do so. Two of these 16 participants left the question unanswered. The written responses of the remaining 14 participants, who could not provide a complete formal definition, are presented below. These responses illustrate how prospective teachers informally conceptualized order relations and constructed their own mental images of the concept (concept definition images).

PT1: “They are relations that show the rules of the relation. For example, if we say $x^2 > y^3$, we order them according to that.”

PT2: “Order relations order things. Wherever ordering is mentioned, there is an order relation. It ensures that the elements we select from a set are ordered according to their comparability.”

PT3: “Order relations order things”

PT4: “Relations that have the properties of reflexivity, anti-symmetry, and transitivity are called order relations.”

PT5: “A order relation is a relation in which ordered pairs are arranged according to a rule.”

PT6: “They are relations that are expressed as ordered pairs, such that (a, b) is expressed as $b > a$ or $a < b$.”

To complement the written responses, excerpts from the interviews regarding the 5th question of OCKT are provided below:

RS: “What is an order relation? How do you define an order relation mathematically?”

PT1: “The relations that satisfy the properties of reflexivity, anti-symmetry, and transitivity are called order relations.”

PT2: “I can't answer.”

PT3: “We call relations that have the properties of anti-symmetry, reflexivity, and transitivity order relations. I can define it this way.”

RS: “Alright, is there a connection between order relations and the concept of ordering?”

PT1: “I don't know exactly.”

PT3: “I think so. We order elements to satisfy the properties of reflexivity, anti-symmetry and transitivity. I don't know if there is another connection.”

As seen above, although PT1 and PT3 were able to articulate the formal definition of order relations, their responses indicate that their conceptual understanding of the function of order relations remained incomplete.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the findings presented in the previous section, this study discussed the difficulties that prospective teachers faced in transforming their informal understanding of the concept of ordering into a formal understanding. These difficulties were examined through their responses to the OCKT both before and after instruction on order relations. The following section also presents suggestions in line with these findings.

When the concept images revealed by the prospective teachers' answers to the OCKT, along with the notations they employed, are evaluated across the B.D and A.D phases, the main difficulties they encountered in the transformation from informal to formal understanding can be summarized as follows:

- ✓ Confusing the concept of ordering with equivalence relations by using the notion of grouping;
- ✓ Restricting ordering to only numerical data or items of the same type;
- ✓ Inadequate use of mathematical notation, which is essential in abstract mathematics, and an overall inability to express ideas in formal mathematical language;
- ✓ Difficulties in comprehending the existence of orderings in real numbers that differ from ordinary ordering, which often contradicts their intuitive perceptions;
- ✓ Struggles in providing a formal definition of order relations, even after instruction;
- ✓ Limited understanding of comparability and incomparability, and an inability to adequately connect these notions with order relations;
- ✓ Challenges in defining an order relation on a given set, particularly the inability to simultaneously satisfy the properties of reflexivity, anti-symmetry, and transitivity.

In this study, it was observed that the concept images of prospective teachers regarding the concept of ordering, derived from their informal knowledge base, were significantly different from one another. This variation is not unexpected, as ordering is a concept about which individuals may only hold vague or intuitive ideas in daily life. Therefore, it is natural for diverse perspectives to emerge before prospective teachers formally encounter the topic.

In the question that asked prospective teachers whether the seemingly unrelated symbols Δ , \triangle , $\#$, and $*$ could be ordered, the responses (Table 2) showed that many participants informally attempted to order these symbols by *determining an arbitrary rule, using permutation, or using combination*. Meanwhile, concept images based on incorrect assumptions—such as “cannot be ordered because no rule/criteria are given” (13), “the necessity of common features among the elements to be ordered” (15), and “only the numerical data can be ordered” (7)—decreased significantly in the A.D phase.

At the formal level, 51 prospective teachers attempted to order the symbols using an appropriate order relation. However, this proportion indicates that the ability to define and apply an order relation to such cases remains limited. In other words, some prospective teachers struggled to connect the ordering of unrelated symbols with a formal order relation. This difficulty can be explained by the fact that, even after instruction, the process of ordering unrelated symbols often contradicts the intuitive conceptions of ordering that prospective teachers develop through everyday experience.

The findings reveal that most prospective teachers felt the need for a specific criterion or rule in the first question of the OCKT, which investigates their thoughts about the concept of ordering. This is understandable, since in daily life we often rely on explicit rules to order objects or items. However, from the perspective of developing a formal understanding, what is expected of prospective teachers is to associate the concept of ordering with order relations, thereby addressing the perceived need for criteria through the formal properties of order relations.

Even after prospective teachers had formally encountered the concept of ordering, only 23% directly associated it with order relations, indicating persistent difficulties in this regard. This may stem from the

fact that in daily life, when ordering is mentioned, students tend to overlook the underlying mathematical structure—namely, order relations—or push it into the background. Indeed, as shown in the findings, none of the responses to the first question of the OCKT at the informal level reflected an image of order relations. One underlying reason may be that in abstract mathematics courses; educators do not sufficiently highlight this critical aspect of order relations during instruction.

It can be argued that some prospective teachers had difficulty associating the ordering of seemingly unrelated symbols with an order relation. This difficulty may be explained by the fact that ordering such symbols often contradicts the intuitive conceptions that prospective teachers hold about ordering in daily life.

In the fourth question of the OCKT, which asked whether there can be elements in a set that cannot be compared with each other, 79% of prospective teachers—after formal instruction on order relations—were able to define an appropriate order relation and demonstrate that incomparability among elements is possible. However, 21% of the participants continued to experience difficulties in determining whether elements could be compared. Moreover, some prospective teachers at the formal level still exhibited misconceptions, such as believing that only numerical data can be compared or that elements lacking a common feature cannot be compared. As shown in Table 4, this suggests that a considerable portion of prospective teachers (51 + 27) were still influenced by these two concept images.

In the fifth question of the OCKT, which asked participants to define the concept of order relations, 16% of prospective teachers were still unable to provide a formal definition even after instruction. Their responses consisted of informal or incomplete definitions, some of which are presented in the findings section. The persistence of such difficulties highlights a critical challenge in fostering formal understanding, as some definitions also revealed confusion between order relations and equivalence relations. Since precise definitions are of paramount importance in an axiomatic discipline such as mathematics, it is essential that educators place sufficient emphasis on definitions when teaching abstract mathematics courses.

SUGGESTIONS FOR PRACTICE AND FURTHER RESEARCH

- ✓ Since prospective teachers' understanding of ordering is dominated by the ordinary order of real numbers, abstract mathematics courses should emphasize that different orderings are possible by defining appropriate order relations on different sets. This could help challenge the belief that only numerical data or items with common features can be ordered.
- ✓ Some prospective teachers associate ordering with grouping and classifying elements. Educators should explicitly highlight that grouping is consistent with equivalence relations, not order relations. Clarifying this distinction can help prospective teachers develop more accurate concept images of ordering.
- ✓ Prospective teachers' ability to use mathematical notation, a crucial aspect of abstract mathematics, should be improved. Greater emphasis should be placed on the meaning of mathematical representations and symbols, and students should be given sufficient time to reflect on representations and proofs. This would help prevent rote memorization and encourage deeper conceptual understanding. Further mathematics education research could investigate prospective teachers' ability to use notation in proofs and definitions across different sample groups.
- ✓ Educators should ensure that prospective teachers do not merely memorize the properties of reflexivity, anti-symmetry, and transitivity. Instead, they should be encouraged to critically question why these properties characterize order or equivalence relations.
- ✓ Abstract mathematics courses should include exercises that require prospective teachers to define order relations on given sets under predetermined conditions. Such practice could help them overcome difficulties in representing order relations in the form of ordered pairs.
- ✓ Instruction should stress that, under a given order relation, not all elements of a set can necessarily be compared. Emphasizing the possibility of incomparability can help correct misconceptions regarding universal comparability.

- ✓ Because the abstract nature of concepts in mathematics often challenges learners, instruction should incorporate connections to daily-life contexts whenever possible to support the transition from informal to formal understanding.
- ✓ Future research could extend this study with larger sample groups and different theoretical perspectives, such as the APOS framework proposed by Dubinsky and McDonald (2001).

Ethics and Conflict of Interest

The author affirms adherence to ethical guidelines throughout the research process. No conflict of interest is declared.

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